

Seeing the unseen: The neurodevelopmental factors related to visual impairments in children with unilateral cerebral palsy

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ABBREVIATIONS

AUC Area under the curve

Beery-VMI Beery Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition

CC Corpus callosum

CP Cerebral palsy

CVI Cerebral Visual Impairment

FCVIQ Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire

MACS Manual Ability Classification System

MRICS Magnetic resonance imaging classification system

NPV Negative predictive value

PPV Positive predictive value

PVL Periventricular leukomalacia

sMRI Structural magnetic resonance imaging

TVPS-4 Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition

uCP Unilateral cerebral palsy

VMI Visuomotor integration

WM White matter

Abstract

Background: In children with unilateral cerebral palsy (uCP), the relation between different factors (brain damage, prematurity, and CP side) and visual impairments, which are common but often ‘unseen’, is not fully understood.

Methods: Visual functions and functional vision were assessed in 41 children with uCP (7-15y, 21 left-sided, 19 preterm). Brain damage was scored on structural MRI regarding lesion timing, location, and severity, and corpus callosum (CC) length and splenium thickness. With non-parametric statistics we investigated the relation between visual outcomes and brain damage (r_s) and differences in visual outcomes and brain damage based on prematurity and uCP side (r). With elastic-net regularized regression models (AUC; d) we explored if gestational age and brain damage could predict impairments in visual functions.

Results: Damage to the lobes and CC was associated with reduced visual functions and functional vision ($r_s=-0.402$ to -0.611). Compared to children born at term, preterm children mainly showed reduced geniculostriate functions ($r=0.343-0.443$) and damage to the parietal lobe ($r=0.353$). No differences in brain damage were found between children with left and right-sided uCP. In regression models, shorter CC length and parietal lobe lesion ($d=-0.526$ to 0.564) were the main predictors for impaired stereoacuity (AUC=0.77), and occipital lobe lesion ($d=0.349$) for impaired visuomotor integration (AUC=0.81). Prediction models of visual perception showed poor predictive performance (AUC<0.70).

Conclusions: Specific brain damage and prematurity are related to different visual impairments in children with uCP. Our results could guide clinicians in prioritizing specific visual assessments and subsequent early intervention in children with uCP.

Keywords Unilateral cerebral palsy; visual impairments; functional vision; brain damage; corpus callosum

1. INTRODUCTION

Impairments in visual functions are common but often not “directly visible” in children with spastic unilateral cerebral palsy (uCP), a neurodevelopmental disability caused by brain damage occurring in the developing or infant brain.^{1,2} Spastic CP is the prevailing subtype, defined as unilateral (44%) if sensorimotor impairments are predominantly present on one side of the body.³ Besides motor areas, early brain lesions can affect the visual system of children with uCP, resulting in reduced geniculostriate and visual-perceptual functions.⁴ Although visual impairments are less obvious than motor problems, they can severely impact the use of vision in daily activities (i.e., functional vision)⁵ and the quality of life of children with uCP. To be able to better predict visual difficulties, several studies attempted to identify a relation between visual impairments and neurodevelopmental factors such as brain damage, prematurity of birth, and the side of CP, reporting no clear relation between visual functions and specific brain structure and mixed results on the relation with prematurity and right or left-sided CP.^{4,6,7}

This is not surprising since the visual system entails a complex brain network, involving multiple connections between the thalami, corpus callosum (CC), occipital cortex, and extrastriate visual areas.^{8,9} Visual impairments can result from damage to the anterior visual pathway and/or to the retrochiasmatic visual structures.⁸ Commonly, the visual network is divided into two interacting pathways, the dorsal and ventral stream, responsible for distinct visual functions.¹⁰ The dorsal stream, running between the occipital and the posterior parietal cortex, supports objects' location and motion detection, while the ventral stream, connecting the occipital and temporal cortex, is involved in object perception.^{8,10}

Qualitative¹¹ and semi-quantitative¹² methods of structural magnetic resonance imaging (sMRI) analysis have been used to classify lesion timing, location, and severity in children with CP.^{4,13} In a recent systematic review, we showed that white matter (WM) lesions, particularly periventricular leukomalacia (PVL), are most frequently associated with visual impairments in

children with CP. However, we found limited research on the prevalence of specific visual impairments in relation to particular visual structures in this population.⁴ In children with bilateral CP, research did show that damage to the occipital cortex primarily compromises geniculostriate function, while subcortical damage mainly affects oculomotor function.⁷ Additionally, it is well established that the occipital cortex is functionally connected with the thalami and the posterior part of the CC,^{14,15} structures frequently damaged in children with CP.^{16,17} Although previous findings demonstrated that worse visual functions are related to damage to the thalami in infants with CP and PVL,¹⁸ and to reduced CC biometry in children with developmental disorders and preterm birth (gestational age <37 weeks),¹⁹⁻²¹ this relation remains under-investigated in children with uCP.

PVL is also the most frequent lesion type related to preterm birth, responsible for about half of the children diagnosed with CP.²²⁻²⁴ Previous studies showed that children born preterm without CP, more frequently present with reduced visual acuity, stereopsis, visual perception, and visuomotor integration compared to children born at term.^{25,26} However, studies on children with bilateral CP do not suggest a correlation between gestational age and visual impairments or brain damage.⁷ Lastly, previous research found that children with left-sided uCP perform worse on visual perceptual tests than children with neurotypical development (NTD) or right-sided uCP.^{6,27} Although the authors explained it by suggesting that the right hemisphere is responsible for visuospatial function, they did not include brain damage data.^{6,27} In our previous work, we found no differences between children with left and right-sided uCP on visual perceptual tests while only children with left-sided uCP presented with worse stereoacuity compared to NTD, supporting the hypothesis that the right parietal posterior cortex is responsible for 3D depth perception.² Despite the importance of these findings, previous research focused only on a specific factor or type of visual impairment, highlighting the need for studies including a more comprehensive analysis.

Therefore, the present study aims to (1) describe differences in visual outcomes and structural brain damage between children with uCP born preterm and at term and between children with left and right-sided uCP, (2) systematically investigate the relation between visual outcomes and brain damage in children with uCP, and (3) explore to which extent differences in gestational age and brain damage can predict visual impairments in this population.

2. METHODS

2.1. Participants and procedure

Children with spastic uCP were recruited via the CP care program of the University Hospitals Leuven (Belgium) to take part in this cross-sectional study if they were aged between 7 to 15 and they were able to understand the test instructions. Since these study data are part of a larger project involving upper-limb assessments, a full overview of the inclusion and exclusion criteria can be found in Crotti et al.^{2,28} Perinatal variables, the side of uCP (i.e., the side of the body mainly impaired), and the level of manual ability, classified according to the Manual Ability Classification System (MACS),²⁹ were retrieved from medical records. Visual assessments and MRI were performed in a single day or split into two half days according to the family's preference. Consent to participate was provided by parents and children older than 12 years. This study was approved by the UZ/KU Leuven Ethical Committee (S62906).

2.2. Measures

2.2.1. Visual assessments

Standardized and age-appropriate tests, performed with both eyes open and best-corrected vision, were used to assess visual functions and functional vision. A full description of the assessments performed and the cut-offs used to score visual impairments can be found in Crotti et al.²

- *Visual acuity (VA)* was investigated using the Freiburg Visual Acuity Test (FrACT) software³⁰ and scored as a continuous variable in LogMAR, where higher values reflect lower levels of visual acuity.
- *Binocular stereoacuity* was investigated using the fly and the circle subtests of Titmus Stereo Fly,³¹ with higher values indicating better stereoacuity.
- *Motor-free visual-perceptual skills* were assessed using five subtests of the Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition (TVPS-4), namely visual discrimination, spatial relationships, form constancy, visual figure-ground, and visual closure.³²
- *Visuomotor integration* was assessed with the visuomotor integration subtest (VMI) of the Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition (Beery-VMI).³³

After being transformed according to (chronologically) age-equivalent scores from the manuals, the scaled scores of the TVPS-4 subtests and the standard scores of the VMI were transformed into standardized *z*-scores (mean=0, SD=1).

- Functional vision was assessed using the Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire (FCVIQ), a 46-item binary-response tool filled by parents.³⁴ Responses were calculated as a total score [0-46] given by the sum of the ‘yes’ items (1: the child presents the characteristic described in the item; 0: characteristic not present), where a higher score reflects a higher level of functional vision impairment.

2.2.2. Structural MRI

A 3.0 Tesla MRI scanner (Hercules, Philips Medical Systems, Best, The Netherlands) with a 32-channel head coil was used to acquire T1-weighted images (TE/TR/TI 4.2/9.1/760.3 ms, voxel size:0.9×0.9×0.9 mm³), T2-weighted images (TE/TR/TI 280/3000/548 ms, voxel size:1×1×1 mm³), and T2 fluid attenuation inversion recovery (FLAIR) images (TE/TR/TI 283/4800/1650 ms, voxel size:1×1×1 mm³). To familiarize younger children with the MRI scan, a space-themed familiarization protocol was implemented.³⁵ Anatomical images were scored

by a trained researcher (M.C.) and a child neurologist (E.O.) using MRICroGL (version 1.2.2021)³⁶ for lesion timing and severity and the MRI viewer of the clinical working station of the University Hospitals of Leuven for CC biometry.

2.2.2.1. MRI classification system (MRICS) for lesion timing

Lesion timing was classified on T1 and T2-weighted images according to the MRI classification system (MRICS).¹¹ Results were reported as categorical variables, namely maldevelopments (A), predominant WM injury (B), predominant grey matter injury (C), miscellaneous (D), and normal (E).

2.2.2.2. Semi-quantitative scale for lesion location and severity

Lesion location and severity were assessed on FLAIR anatomical images using a semi-quantitative scale validated for children with CP.¹² According to this method of Fiori et al.,¹² brain lesions were graphically represented on a six-axial-slices template. Raw scores were calculated for the WM of each lobe (occipital, parietal, temporal, and frontal), subcortical structures (lenticular, caudate, posterior limb of the internal capsule, thalamus, and brainstem), CC (posterior, anterior, middle), and cerebellum. Summary scores were calculated for the occipital, parietal, temporal, and frontal lobar score (sum of the right and left scores for each lobe; [0-6]), subcortical score (sum of the right and left scores of the subcortical structures; [0-10]), and global score (sum of lobar, subcortical, CC, and cerebellum scores, [0-40]) where higher scores represent more severe brain lesions. Since in the present study, we aimed to investigate the specific role of the thalami and CC in relation to visual function outcomes, in addition to the summary scores, the scores of the thalami (sum of left and right thalamus; [0-2]), total CC (sum of the three parts; [0-3]), and posterior CC [0-1] were included in our analysis.

2.2.2.3. Corpus callosum biometry

Two linear parameters, namely CC length and splenium thickness, were manually measured according to Garel et al.³⁷ in millimeters (*mm*), on the mid-sagittal plane of T1-

weighted images. The length of the CC was measured as the distance between the most anterior part and the most posterior part of the CC, while splenium thickness was calculated by tracing a perpendicular line to the curvilinear axis of the CC at the level of the splenium.³⁷ Other CC measurements were not performed since the splenium is the CC part connecting the temporo-parietal-occipital areas known to be involved in visual functions.³⁸ Additionally, results were classified as above or below the median, according to age-normative values reported by Garel et al.³⁷

2.3. Statistical analyses

Frequencies were calculated for descriptive characteristics, visual outcomes, and brain damage. Since our data deviated from a normal distribution, non-parametric statistics were performed, reporting medians and interquartile ranges. Data were analysed using R (version 4.3.2).

2.3.1. Differences in visual outcomes and brain damage between children with uCP born preterm and at term and between children with left and right-sided uCP

Mann–Whitney *U* tests were performed to investigate differences in visual outcomes and brain damage between children with uCP born preterm and at term and to investigate differences in brain damage between children with left and right-sided uCP. Effect sizes were calculated using correlation coefficients (*r*) and interpreted as small (<0.3), medium (0.3–0.5), or large (≥ 0.5).³⁹

2.3.2. The relation between visual outcomes and brain damage

To study the univariate associations between visual functions, functional vision, and brain damage, pairwise partial Spearman's Rank correlations, corrected for gestational age, were performed using a false discovery rate (adjusted *p*-value ≤ 0.05) for multiple testing

correction.⁴⁰ Correlation coefficients (r_s) were interpreted as no or negligible (<0.30), low ($0.30-0.49$), moderate ($0.50-0.69$), high ($0.70-0.89$), or very high (≥ 0.90).³⁹

2.3.3. Predicting visual impairments with gestational age and sMRI

To explore if differences in gestational age and brain damage can predict visual impairments in children with uCP, elastic-net regularized regression prediction models, with a nested cross-validation approach, were used. The full procedure has been described in a previous publication.⁴¹ Only children with complete data were included ($n=38$). The results from the semi-quantitative scale and CC biometry that showed significant partial Spearman's Rank correlations as well as the gestational age of the participants were standardized and used as predictors. Results of the visual assessments scored as normal or impaired² were included as binary outcomes of the models. Due to the nested cross-validation, each visual outcome was required to have enough participants ($n>4$) in each group (impaired/normal) to be included in the analysis. Therefore, no prediction model was performed on the results of the FrACT test since only four children had impaired visual acuity. Additionally, no prediction model was performed on the results of functional vision since there is no cut-off available in the literature for the FCVIQ. The predictions were compared with the actual visual assessment results to calculate the area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC), sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, positive predictive value (PPV), and negative predictive value (NPV). The predictive power of each model was evaluated using the AUC as no (≤ 0.49), poor ($0.50-0.69$), acceptable ($0.70-0.79$), good ($0.8-0.89$), or outstanding (≥ 0.9) discrimination.⁴² The effect size of each predictor was interpreted according to Cohen's $|d|$ as tiny (< 0.10), very small ($0.10-0.19$), small ($0.20-0.49$), moderate ($0.50-0.79$), large ($0.80-1.19$), very large ($1.20-1.99$), and huge (≥ 2.00).⁴³

3. RESULTS

3.1. Participants

Forty-one children with uCP (mean age 11y6mo, SD 2y19mo, 22 males, 21 left-sided uCP, 19 preterm) were included in this study. Descriptive characteristics and the prevalence of visual impairments and brain damage in our sample are presented in **Table 1** and **Table S1**, respectively. A detailed overview of missing data is presented in **Figure A.1**.

3.2. Descriptive results of visual assessments and brain damage in children with uCP

The majority of children in our sample (68%) had white matter lesions (**Table 1**). All children with impaired visual acuity ($n=4$) had predominantly WM lesions. In children with impaired stereoacuity ($n=14$), 7% presented with maldevelopments (A), 79% with predominantly WM lesions (B), and 14 % with predominantly grey matter lesions (C). Depending on the different TVPS-4 subtests, in children with impaired visual perception ($n=11-18$), 8% to 18% of the children presented with maldevelopments, 57% to 73% with predominantly WM lesions, and 9% to 29% with predominantly grey matter lesions. In children with impaired VMI ($n=24$), 4% presented with maldevelopments, 71% with predominantly WM lesions, and 25% with predominantly grey matter lesions. No visual impairments were found in children with miscellaneous lesions (D) and normal MRI (E) (**Figure 1a**).

The majority of children with uCP born preterm ($n=19$) presented with WM lesions ($n=16$; 84%), followed by grey matter lesions ($n=2$; 11%), and miscellaneous lesions ($n=1$; 5%). Overall, most children with visual impairments were preterm with predominantly WM lesions (**Figure 1b**). Damage to the WM lobes, particularly in the temporal area (93%), was most frequently reported compared to other structural damage (**Table 2**).

3.3. Differences in visual outcomes and brain damage on sMRI based on prematurity and uCP side

Compared to children with uCP born at term, preterm children showed worse visual acuity ($p=0.005$; $r=0.443$), stereoacuity ($p=0.03$; $r=0.343$), and visual perception on the TVPS-

4 subtest form constancy ($p=0.048$; $r=0.312$), and more severe brain damage in the WM of parietal ($p=0.025$; $r=0.353$) and occipital lobes ($p=0.048$; $r=0.312$) (**Table 3**). No significant differences were found for brain damage outcomes between children with left and right-sided uCP.

3.4. The relation between visual outcomes and brain damage in children with uCP

Figure 2 shows the significant Spearman's Rank correlations corrected for gestational age between visual outcomes and brain damage in children with uCP after applying false discovery rate correction. A full overview of the partial Spearman's Rank correlations is presented in **Table S2**. Low to moderate correlations were found between increased damage to the WM lobes ($r_s=-0.402-0.529$, $p=0.049-0.011$), global scores ($r_s=0.486$ to -0.555 , $p=0.018-0.011$), and more impaired visual acuity, stereoacuity, VMI, and the FCVIQ. Total CC ($r_s=0.411$ to -0.611 , $p=0.042-0.004$) and posterior CC scores ($r_s=-0.449$ to -0.458 , $p=0.023-0.019$) of the semi-quantitative scale mainly correlated, with low to moderate correlation coefficients, with stereoacuity and VMI. Reduced CC length ($r_s=-0.463$ to -0.542 , $p=0.019-0.011$) was correlated with lower scores on visual acuity, stereoacuity, motor-free visual perceptual functions, and FCVIQ, while reduced splenium thickness ($r_s=0.428$ to -0.456 , $p=0.031-0.021$) correlated with the TVPS-4 subtest form constancy and the FCVIQ. No correlations were found between visual outcomes and thalamic and subcortical scores.

3.5. Predicting visual impairments with gestational age and sMRI

A detailed overview of the AUC, sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, PPV, and NPV for each model of the elastic-net regularized regression analysis is presented in **Table 4**, and the estimates of the individual predictors are reported in **Table 5**. In the sections below, we present only the main predictors, showing small to moderate effect sizes, for the models with at least an acceptable discrimination ($AUC>0.70$) (**Figure 3**).

For impairments in *stereoacuity*, the model had acceptable discrimination (AUC=0.77), with damage to the parietal lobe WM ($d=0.564$) and reduced CC length ($d=-0.526$) showing moderate effect sizes, and gestational age ($d=-0.448$) and damage to the total CC ($d=0.300$) small effect sizes. For impairments in *visual perception*, the models predicting the TVPS-4 subtests results had poor discrimination (AUC=0.53-0.67). Remarkably, with the available data, we were not able to fit an adequate model for the results of the TVPS-4 subtest visual closure. For impairments in *visuomotor integration*, the model had good discrimination (AUC=0.81), with damage to the temporal and occipital WM lobe, and the global score showing small effect sizes ($d=0.202-0.349$).

DISCUSSION

In this study, we investigated the relation between visual outcomes and different neurodevelopmental factors showing that prematurity of birth and WM and CC damage impact visual outcomes, while children with left and right-sided uCP did not show any differences in visual functions and brain damage. For all visual functions, the majority of children with impairments were preterm with predominantly WM lesions. Children born preterm ($n=19$, 46%) showed mainly reduced geniculostriate functions (i.e. visual acuity and binocular stereoacuity) and damage to the WM parietal lobe compared to children born at term. Additionally, we found that CC damage and length were related to nearly all visual outcomes while, depending on the location (frontal, occipital, parietal, temporal), damage to the WM lobes was related only to specific visual outcomes. Lastly, the models of impaired stereoacuity and VMI showed acceptable discrimination, with shorter CC length and parietal lobe lesions being the most significant predictors for impaired stereoacuity, and occipital lobe lesions for impaired VMI.

Different mechanisms underlie the development of specific visual functions, particularly in children with brain damage. Visual acuity and stereoacuity develop with the

formation of the connections between the thalami and the occipital cortex, which start emerging in utero. In the case of perinatal hypoxic-ischaemic events (PVL), occurring between 24 and 34 weeks gestation due to premature birth, normal geniculostriate function development might be impaired.⁴⁴ In contrast, the WM tracts responsible for visual perception and visuomotor functions could be less affected by prematurity, since the myelination process continues after birth and up to 9 years within the extrastriate visual cortex maturation.⁴⁵ Additionally, we found more severe parietal lobe WM lesions in children born preterm, in line with the theory that preterm birth has a more profound effect on the dorsal compared to the ventral visual stream.⁴⁵ The lack of a relation between gestational age and the severity of visual impairments or brain damage in other studies on children with CP,^{7,46} might be due to the types of visual functions assessed (e.g., mainly oculomotor and geniculostriate impairments summed up in a visual total score) and the limited scores of brain damage they included.^{7,46} Lastly, we found no differences in brain damage between children with left and right-sided uCP. This could be attributed to the presence of widespread (bilateral) lesions in our cohort while the classification (i.e., right/left-sided uCP) is based on their clinical motor performance, which does not always accurately reflect the presence of bilateral lesions. Therefore, further studies including participants with more focal and unilateral brain lesions (i.e., children with congenital stroke), are needed to further investigate differences in visual outcomes in children with uCP.

Brain damage was assessed using the MRICS, a semi-quantitative scale, and CC biometry, all easily accessible methods to clinicians. In line with previous findings, we showed that higher global scores on the semi-quantitative scale were associated with reduced geniculostriate functions.⁷ Additionally, we found that higher global scores were also related to reduced VMI and functional vision and reduced CC biometry to reduced geniculostriate function, visual perception, and functional vision in children with uCP.

According to the literature, both reduced visual acuity and stereoacuity were associated with WM parietal lobe damage and reduced CC length.⁴⁷⁻⁵⁰ Additionally, reduced *stereoacuity* was also related to frontal, temporal, and CC damage, suggesting that 3D perception might rely on a more complex brain network compared to visual acuity. Results on stereoacuity were supported by the regression analysis, in which damage to the WM parietal lobe was the main predictor of impairments in this function, in line with the hypothesis that the parietal posterior cortex is responsible for 3D perception.⁴⁹ Additional significant predictors were lower gestational age, reduced CC length, and more severe CC damage on the semi-quantitative scale, in line with studies on impaired stereoacuity in children at 4 years of age born preterm.²⁰ Our results further extend these findings to school-aged children with uCP, supporting the role of CC in the binocular integration of 3D stimuli.^{51,52}

Inferences on the relation between *visual perception* outcomes and brain damage are difficult to make since the correlation analysis reported limited associations and the regression models showed no or poor discrimination performances. A possible explanation is that visual perception includes complex functions in which connections between brain areas rather than single lobes are involved, as partially supported by our results showing a positive relation between lower scores on TVPS-4 subtests and shorter CC length. Hence, further studies involving more complex techniques (e.g., diffusion MRI, fMRI) might help to better understand the underlying mechanism of visual perception.

Lower scores on the *VMI* were associated with temporal, occipital WM lobe, and CC damage, supporting the involvement of the ventral stream in object identification and the role of the CC in visuomotor processing. These results were partially supported by the elastic-net regression analysis, showing that more severe temporal, occipital WM lobe damage and higher global score of the semi-quantitative scale are potentially useful predictors of impaired VMI. Lastly, higher scores of the *FCVIQ* were associated with damage to the frontal, temporal WM

lobes, and CC. These relations might be explained within the framework of the temporal cortex attention network and the involvement of the frontal lobe in cognitive functions.^{53,54} Indeed the FCVIQ items reported more frequently by parents were related to visual attention and complex problem-solving. Additionally, both attention and cognitive functions require good inter-hemispheric connections, which could explain the relation between the FCVIQ scores and damage to the CC.⁵⁵ However, no prediction model could be performed on impairment in functional vision, since no cut-off is described for the FCVIQ.

Remarkably, although 39% of children presented with lesions to the thalami, in contrast with previous findings, no association was found with visual outcomes.⁷ Differences could be explained by the fact that we did not include a visual total score, but we specifically studied different visual functions. Since the role of the thalami in visual development is well recognized,¹⁸ further studies using automatic brain parcellation⁵⁶ and diffusion MRI might help in elucidating the relation between the thalami and specific visual functions in children with uCP.

Overall, in the regression analysis, we acknowledge that only the models of impaired stereoacuity and visuomotor integration showed at least acceptable discrimination, with tiny to moderate effect sizes. A possible explanation is the relatively small sample size, which could lead to imprecise parameter estimates of the regression models. Nevertheless, we performed elastic-net regularized regression which allowed to handle more predictors compared to the sample size,⁵⁷ compensating for the risk of overfitting. Additionally, to the researcher's knowledge, for the first time, we showed that specific brain damage and differences in gestational age can predict distinct visual impairments in children with uCP. Despite its limitations and the explorative nature of our study, our findings are promising since they can be the starting point to understand, based on standardized methods accessible to clinicians,

which visual functions could be more at risk of impairments based on early brain injury in children with uCP.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, using sMRI scoring methods, we first showed that in children with uCP prematurity is mainly related to reduced geniculostriate functions and parietal lobe WM lesions. Secondly, we found that CC damage and length are related to nearly all visual outcomes, while the relation between visual functions and WM lobe damage depends on the location. Lastly, our explorative analysis suggests that lesions to the WM lobes and reduced CC length are potentially useful predictors of stereoacuity and VMI impairments in children with uCP. Our results could guide clinicians in prioritizing specific visual assessments based on early brain injury, to prevent visual function worsening that can severely impact the overall functioning and quality of life of children with uCP.

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REFERENCES

- 1 Rosenbaum P, Paneth N, Leviton A, Goldstein M, Bax M, Damiano D *et al.* A report: the definition and classification of cerebral palsy April 2006. *Dev Med Child Neurol Suppl* 2007; **109**: 8–14.
- 2 Crotti M, Ortibus E, Maillieux L, Decraene L, Kleeren L, Ben Itzhak N. Visual, perceptual functions, and functional vision in children with unilateral cerebral palsy compared to children with neurotypical development. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 2024. doi:10.1111/dmcn.15842.
- 3 Himmelmann K, Uvebrant P. The panorama of cerebral palsy in Sweden part XII shows that patterns changed in the birth years 2007–2010. *Acta Paediatr* 2018; **107**: 462–468.
- 4 Crotti M, Genoe S, Ben Itzhak N, Maillieux L, Ortibus E. The relation between neuroimaging and visual impairment in children and adolescents with cerebral palsy: A systematic review. *Brain Dev* 2023; : S0387760423001729.
- 5 Colenbrander A. Visual functions and functional vision. *Int Congr Ser* 2005; **1282**: 482–486.
- 6 Berelowitz S, Franzsen D. Visual Perceptual Deficits in Different Types of Cerebral Palsy. *South Afr J Occup Ther* 2021; **51**. doi:10.17159/2310-3833/2021/vol51n1a4.
- 7 Tinelli F, Guzzetta A, Purpura G, Pasquariello R, Cioni G, Fiori S. Structural brain damage and visual disorders in children with cerebral palsy due to periventricular leukomalacia. *NeuroImage Clin* 2020; **28**: 102430.
- 8 Swienton DJ, Thomas AG. The Visual Pathway—Functional Anatomy and Pathology. *Semin Ultrasound CT MRI* 2014; **35**: 487–503.
- 9 Braddick O, Atkinson J. Development of human visual function. *Vision Res* 2011; **51**: 1588–1609.
- 10 Pisella L, Binkofski F, Lasek K, Toni I, Rossetti Y. No double-dissociation between optic ataxia and visual agnosia: Multiple sub-streams for multiple visuo-manual integrations. *Neuropsychologia* 2006; **44**: 2734–2748.
- 11 Himmelmann K, Horber V, De La Cruz J, Horridge K, Mejaski-Bosnjak V, Hollody K *et al.* MRI classification system (MRICS) for children with cerebral palsy: development, reliability, and recommendations. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 2017; **59**: 57–64.
- 12 Fiori S, Cioni G, Klingels K, Ortibus E, Van Gestel L, Rose S *et al.* Reliability of a novel, semi-quantitative scale for classification of structural brain magnetic resonance imaging in children with cerebral palsy. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 2014; **56**: 839–845.
- 13 Hoon AH, Faria AV. Pathogenesis, Neuroimaging and Management in Children With Cerebral Palsy Born Preterm. *Dev Disabil Res Rev* 2010; **16**: 302–312.
- 14 Usrey WM, Alitto HJ. Visual Functions of the Thalamus. *Annu Rev Vis Sci* 2015; **1**: 351–371.

- 15 van Meer N, Houtman AC, Van Schuerbeek P, Vanderhasselt T, Milleret C, ten Tusscher MP. Interhemispheric Connections between the Primary Visual Cortical Areas via the Anterior Commissure in Human Callosal Agenesis. *Front Syst Neurosci* 2016; **10**: 101.
- 16 Mailleux L, Franki I, Emsell L, Peedima M-L, Fehrenbach A, Feys H *et al*. The relationship between neuroimaging and motor outcome in children with cerebral palsy: A systematic review—Part B diffusion imaging and tractography. *Res Dev Disabil* 2020; **97**: 103569.
- 17 Ilves N, Lõo S, Ilves N, Laugesaar R, Looits D, Kool P *et al*. Ipsilesional volume loss of basal ganglia and thalamus is associated with poor hand function after ischemic perinatal stroke. *BMC Neurol* 2022; **22**: 23.
- 18 Ricci D, Anker S, Cowan F, Pane M, Gallini F, Luciano R *et al*. Thalamic atrophy in infants with PVL and cerebral visual impairment. *Early Hum Dev* 2006; **82**: 591–595.
- 19 Eken P, de Vries LS, van der Graaf Y, Meiners LC, van Nieuwenhuizen O. Haemorrhagic-ischæmic lesions of the neonatal brain: correlation between cerebral visual impairment, neurodevelopmental outcome and MRI in infancy. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 1995; **37**: 41–55.
- 20 Kwinta P, Herman-Sucharska I, Leśniak A, Klimek M, Karcz P, Durlak W *et al*. Relationship between Stereoscopic Vision, Visual Perception, and Microstructure Changes of Corpus Callosum and Occipital White Matter in the 4-Year-Old Very Low Birth Weight Children. *BioMed Res Int* 2015; **2015**: e842143.
- 21 Van Naarden Braun K, Doernberg N, Schieve L, Christensen D, Goodman A, Yeargin-Allsopp M. Birth Prevalence of Cerebral Palsy: A Population-Based Study. *Pediatrics* 2016; **137**: 1–9.
- 22 Kozeis N, Panos GD, Zafeiriou DI, de Gottrau P, Gatziofias Z. Comparative Study of Refractive Errors, Strabismus, Microsaccades, and Visual Perception Between Preterm and Full-Term Children With Infantile Cerebral Palsy. *J Child Neurol* 2015; **30**: 972–975.
- 23 Volpe JJ. Neurobiology of Periventricular Leukomalacia in the Premature Infant. *Pediatr Res* 2001; **50**: 553–562.
- 24 Favara M, Greenspan J, Aghai ZH. Cerebral Palsy and the Relationship to Prematurity. In: Miller F, Bachrach S, Lennon N, O’Neil ME (eds). *Cerebral Palsy*. Springer International Publishing: Cham, 2020, pp 23–36.
- 25 Cooke RWI. Ophthalmic impairment at 7 years of age in children born very preterm. *Arch Dis Child - Fetal Neonatal Ed* 2004; **89**: F249–F253.
- 26 Ibrahim D, Mendiola Santibañez JD, Rodríguez-Reséndiz J. Visual Performance and Perceptual–Motor Skills of Late Preterm Children and Healthy Controls Using the TVPS-3rd and VMI-6th Editions. *Technologies* 2023; **11**: 53.
- 27 Burtner PA, Dukeminier A, Lynette B, Qualls C, Scott K. Visual Perceptual Skills and Related School Functions in Children with Hemiplegic Cerebral Palsy. *N Z J Occup Ther* 2006; **53**: 24–29.

- 28 Crotti M, Ortibus E, Ben Itzhak N, Kleeren L, Decraene L, Leenaerts N *et al.* The relation between visual functions, functional vision, and bimanual function in children with unilateral cerebral palsy. *Res Dev Disabil* 2024; **152**: 104792.
- 29 Eliasson A-C, Krumlinde-Sundholm L, Rösblad B, Beckung E, Arner M, Ohrvall A-M *et al.* The Manual Ability Classification System (MACS) for children with cerebral palsy: scale development and evidence of validity and reliability. *Dev Med Child Neurol* 2006; **48**: 549–554.
- 30 Bach M. The Freiburg Visual Acuity Test—automatic measurement of visual acuity. *Optom Vis Sci* 1996; **73**.https://journals.lww.com/optvissci/Fulltext/1996/01000/The_Freiburg_Visual_Acuity_Test_Automatic.8.aspx.
- 31 Stereo Optical Corporation. Stereo Fly Test. 2018.<https://www.stereoptical.com/products/stereotests-color-tests/original-stereo-fly/#1529520225990-6a35365b-d00f>.
- 32 Martin N. Test of Visual Perceptual Skills 4th Edition (TVPS-4). 2017.
- 33 Beery KE, Buktenica NA, Beery NA. Developmental Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition, Revised (VMI). *Developmental Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition, Revised (VMI)* 2010.
- 34 Ortibus E, Laenen A, Verhoeven J, De Cock P, Casteels I, Schoolmeesters B *et al.* Screening for Cerebral Visual Impairment: value of a CVI questionnaire. *Neuropediatrics* 2011; **42**: 138–147.
- 35 Verly M, Gerrits R, Sleurs C, Lagae L, Sunaert S, Zink I *et al.* The mis-wired language network in children with developmental language disorder: insights from DTI tractography. *Brain Imaging Behav* 2019; **13**: 973–984.
- 36 NITRC: MRICroGL: Tool/Resource Info. <https://www.nitrc.org/projects/mricrogl> (accessed 17 May2024).
- 37 Garel C, Cont I, Alberti C, Josserand E, Moutard ML, Ducou le Pointe H. Biometry of the corpus callosum in children: MR imaging reference data. *AJNR Am J Neuroradiol* 2011; **32**: 1436–1443.
- 38 Doty RW, Negrão N. Forebrain Commissures and Vision. In: Berlucchi G, Brindley GS, Brooks B, Creutzfeldt OD, Dodt E, Doty RW *et al.* (eds). *Visual Centers in the Brain*. Springer: Berlin, Heidelberg, 1973, pp 543–582.
- 39 Mukaka MM. Statistics corner: A guide to appropriate use of correlation coefficient in medical research. *Malawi Med J J Med Assoc Malawi* 2012; **24**: 69–71.
- 40 Benjamini Y, Hochberg Y. Controlling the false discovery rate: a practical and powerful approach to multiple testing. *J R Stat Soc Ser B Methodol* 1995; **57**: 289–300.
- 41 Leenaerts N, Soyster P, Ceccarini J, Sunaert S, Fisher A, Vrieze E. Person-specific and pooled prediction models for binge eating, alcohol use and binge drinking in bulimia nervosa and alcohol use disorder. *Psychol Med* 2024; : 1–16.

- 42 Hosmer Jr DW, Lemeshow S, Sturdivant RX. *Applied logistic regression*. John Wiley & Sons, 2013.
- 43 Sawilowsky SS. New effect size rules of thumb. *J Mod Appl Stat Methods* 2009; **8**: 597–599.
- 44 Leung MP, Thompson B, Black J, Dai S, Alsweiler JM. The effects of preterm birth on visual development. *Clin Exp Optom* 2018; **101**: 4–12.
- 45 Atkinson J, Braddick O. Visual and visuocognitive development in children born very prematurely. *Prog Brain Res* 2007; **164**: 123–149.
- 46 Errante A, Bozzetti F, Piras A, Beccani L, Filippi M, Costi S *et al*. Lesion mapping and functional characterization of hemiplegic children with different patterns of hand manipulation. *NeuroImage Clin* 2024; **41**: 103575.
- 47 Mitchell DE, Blakemore C. Binocular depth perception and the corpus callosum. *Vision Res* 1970; **10**: 49–54.
- 48 Elberger AJ. The corpus callosum is a critical factor for developing maximum visual acuity. *Brain Res* 1982; **281**: 350–353.
- 49 Nishida Y, Hayashi O, Iwami T, Kimura M, Kani K, Ito R *et al*. Stereopsis-processing regions in the human parieto-occipital cortex. *NeuroReport* 2001; **12**.https://journals.lww.com/neuroreport/Fulltext/2001/07200/Stereopsis_processing_regions_in_the_human.43.aspx.
- 50 Pietrasanta M, Restani L, Caleo M. The Corpus Callosum and the Visual Cortex: Plasticity Is a Game for Two. *Neural Plast* 2012; **2012**: 838672.
- 51 Saint-Amour D, Lepore F, Lassonde M, Guillemot J-P. Effective binocular integration at the midline requires the corpus callosum. *Neuropsychologia* 2004; **42**: 164–174.
- 52 Fisher NF. The Optic Chiasm and the Corpus Callosum: Their Relationship to Binocular Vision in Humans. *J Pediatr Ophthalmol Strabismus* 1986; **23**: 126–131.
- 53 Ramezanpour H, Fallah M. The role of temporal cortex in the control of attention. *Curr Res Neurobiol* 2022; **3**: 100038.
- 54 Fuster JM. Frontal lobe and cognitive development. *J Neurocytol* 2002; **31**: 373–385.
- 55 Hinkley LBN, Marco EJ, Findlay AM, Honma S, Jeremy RJ, Strominger Z *et al*. The Role of Corpus Callosum Development in Functional Connectivity and Cognitive Processing. *PLoS ONE* 2012; **7**: e39804.
- 56 Simarro J, Meyer MI, Van Eyndhoven S, Phan TV, Billiet T, Sima DM *et al*. A deep learning model for brain segmentation across pediatric and adult populations. *Sci Rep* 2024; **14**: 11735.
- 57 Zou H, Hastie T. Regularization and variable selection via the elastic net. *J R Stat Soc Ser B Stat Methodol* 2005; **67**: 301–320.

FIGURES

Figure 1. Visual outcomes in children with unilateral cerebral palsy with different lesion timing classified on the MRICS (a) and distribution of visual impairments in children born at term and preterm (b).

Abbreviations: uCP, unilateral cerebral palsy; FrACT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS-4, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; MRICS, Magnetic Resonance Imaging Classification System: A, maldevelopments; B, predominant white matter injury; C, predominant grey matter injury; D, miscellaneous; E, normal.

Figure 2. Partial Spearman's rank correlation matrix showing the significant correlations between visual outcomes and MRI score and corpus callosum biometry.

Significant results are shown as * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$.

Abbreviations: CC, corpus callosum; FrACT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS-4, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; FCVIQ, Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire.

Figure 3. The predictors of the elastic-net regularized regression models with at least an acceptable discrimination for impairments on the visual assessments. The average estimate is displayed for only the predictors that were included in at least one fold of the leave-one-out-cross-validation.

Abbreviations: GA, gestational age; CC, corpus callosum; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition.

TABLES

Table 1. Clinical characteristics of children with unilateral cerebral palsy.

General characteristics	Category	n	(%)
Mean age (SD), years:months		11:06 (2:09)	
Sex	Male	22	54
	Female	19	46
Side of cerebral palsy	Right-sided	20	49
	Left-sided	21	51
Magnetic Resonance Imaging Classification System category ¹¹	A	2	5
	B	28	68
	C	8	20
	D	1	2
	E	2	5
Manual Ability Classification System level ^{29,a}	I	23	56
	II	14	34
	III	4	10
Gestational age ^{a,b}	Mean (SD), months	36 (3.9)	
	Term	21	51
	Preterm	13	32
	Very preterm	6	15
	Unknown	1	2
Birth weight ^{a,c}	Mean (SD), grams	2828,56 (984,77)	
	Normal	28	68
	Low	12	29
	Unknown ^d	1	3

Percentages are calculated out of the total sample of children with unilateral CP ($n = 41$).

^a Retrieved from medical records.

^b Gestational age refers to completed weeks of pregnancy: term, ≥ 37 to < 42 weeks; preterm, ≥ 32 to < 37 weeks; very preterm, < 32 weeks.

^c Birthweight: normal birthweight, ≥ 2500 g; low birthweight, < 2500 g.

^d Unknown reflects no reported data or missing data, which exists because of the retrospective data retrieval.

Abbreviations: CP, cerebral palsy; SD, standard deviation; A, maldevelopments; B, predominant white matter injury; C, predominant grey matter injury; D, miscellaneous; E, normal.

Table 2. Prevalence of children with impairment in visual function and brain damage quantified on the semi-quantitative scale and CC biometry below the normative range.

	Visual Acuity (n=4)		Stereoaucuity (n=14)		TVPS-4 Visual Discrimination (n=14)		TVPS-4 Spatial Relationships (n=11)		TVPS-4 Form Constancy (n=12)		TVPS-4 Visual Figure-Ground (n=12)		TVPS-4 Visual Closure (n=18)		Beery-Visuomotor integration (n=24)	
	x	%	x	%	x	%	x	%	x	%	x	%	x	%	x	%
Frontal Lobe	4	100	14	100	14	100	11	100	12	100	12	100	18	100	23	96
Temporal Lobe	4	100	14	100	14	100	11	100	12	100	12	100	18	100	24	100
Parietal Lobe	4	100	14	100	14	100	11	100	12	100	12	100	18	100	23	96
Occipital Lobe	4	100	14	100	12	86	9	82	12	100	10	83	17	94	24	100
Thalami	2	50	7	50	6	43	2	18	5	42	4	33	6	33	10	42
Total CC	3	75	13	93	12	86	9	82	9	75	9	75	15	83	22	92
Posterior CC	3	75	13	93	11	79	9	82	8	67	9	75	14	78	21	88
Subcortical	3	75	11	79	13	93	10	91	8	67	11	92	15	83	20	83
Fiori global	4	100	14	100	14	100	11	100	12	100	12	100	18	100	24	100
CC total length	3	75	12	86	13	93	10	91	10	83	10	83	13	72	19	79
Splenium	3	75	11	79	11	79	9	82	10	83	9	75	15	83	20	83

Abbreviations: n, total number of children with impaired visual function; x: total number of children with impaired visual function and lesions or biometry below the median; %, percentage calculated on the total number of children with impaired visual function ($\% = x/n$); CC, corpus callosum; TVPS-4, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; FCVIQ, Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire.

Table 3. Differences in visual outcomes and brain damage between children with uCP born preterm and at term.

	Children with uCP born at term (<i>n</i> =21) Median [IQR]	Children with uCP born preterm (<i>n</i> =19) Median [IQR]	<i>p</i> -value	<i>r</i>
Visual assessments				
^a FrACT	-0.204 [-0.277,-0.088]	-0.033 [-0.122,0.202]	0.005	0.443
^b Titmus Stereo Fly ↑	9 [8,9]	3 [1,9]	0.030	0.343
^c TVPS -Visual Discrimination ↑	-0.333 [-1.333,0.333]	-0.333 [-1.667,0.5]	0.817	0.037
^c TVPS -Spatial Relationships ↑	0 [-0.333,0.667]	0.33 [-1.167,0.667]	0.691	0.063
^c TVPS -Form Constancy ↑	-0.333 [-0.667,1]	-0.667 [-1.333,0.333]	0.048	0.312
^c TVPS -Visual Figure-Ground ↑	0 [-1,0.333]	-0.333 [-1.167,-0.165]	0.384	0.138
^c TVPS -Visual Closure ↑	-0.333 [-1,0.333]	-1 [-1.333,-0.333]	0.075	0.282
^c Beery- Visuomotor integration ↑	-1.1 [-2.117,-0.583]	-1.4 [-2.1,-0.833]	0.527	0.101
^d FCVIQ ↓	4 [1,7]	4.5 [1.25,8.25]	0.955	0.009
Brain damage				
^e Frontal Total ↓	1.5 [1,2]	2 [1.25,2.75]	0.057	0.301
^e Temporal Total ↓	1.5 [1,2]	2 [1.25,2.5]	0.261	0.178
^e Parietal Total ↓	2.5 [1,3]	3 [3,4]	0.025	0.353
^e Occipital Total ↓	1.5 [1,2]	2 [1.5,3]	0.048	0.312
^e Thalamic Total ↓	0 [0,1]	0 [0,1]	0.936	0.013
^e CC posterior ↓	1 [0,1]	1 [0.5,1]	0.433	0.124
^e CC Total ↓	2 [0,2]	2 [1,2]	0.460	0.117
^e Subcortical ↓	2 [1,3]	1 [0,2.5]	0.375	0.140
^e Global score ↓	10 [7,14]	13 [8.75,15.75]	0.143	0.231
^f CC length ↑	65.4 [62.675,69.9]	66.5 [61.6,69.1]	0.704	0.061
^f Splenium thickness ↑	10.1 [9.4,11.5]	9.3 [8.1,10.35]	0.096	0.264

Significant results are shown in bold type: **p* ≤ 0.05, ***p* ≤ 0.01.

^aResults are reported in LogMAR. ^bResults report the last circle identified or the fly test. ^cResults are reported in z-scores.

^dResults calculated as the sum of the 'yes' items (1: the child presents the characteristic described in the item). ^eResults of the semiquantitative scale. ^fResults of CC biometry calculated in *mm*. ↑: higher values indicate a better performance or less severe brain damage. ↓: lower values indicate a better performance or more severe brain damage.

Abbreviations: *n*, number of children; IQR, interquartile range; *r*, effect size calculated as correlation coefficients and interpreted as small (<0.3), medium (0.3–0.5), or large (≥0.5)³⁹; FrACT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; FCVIQ, Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire; CC, corpus callosum.

Table 4. Performance of the models on the prediction of visual impairments in children with uCP.

	AUC	Sensitivity	Specificity	Accuracy	PPV	NPV
Titmus stereo Fly	0.77	0.71	0.83	0.79	0.71	0.83
TVPS -Visual Discrimination	<i>0.67</i>	0.71	0.67	0.68	0.56	0.80
TVPS -Spatial Relationships	<i>0.56</i>	0.55	0.67	0.63	0.40	0.78
TVPS -Form Constancy	<i>0.54</i>	0.50	0.69	0.63	0.43	0.75
TVPS -Visual Figure-Ground	<i>0.53</i>	0.50	0.73	0.66	0.46	0.76
Beery- Visuomotor integration	0.81	0.63	0.93	0.74	0.94	0.59

Abbreviations: AUC, area under the curve used to evaluate the model performance and interpreted with no (≤ 0.49), poor (0.50-0.69) in italics, acceptable (0.70-0.79) in bold italics, good (0.80-0.89) in bold, or outstanding (≥ 0.9) discrimination;⁴² NPV, negative predictive value; PPV, positive predictive value; TVPS-4, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition.

Table 5. Results of the elastic-net regularized regression with the effect sizes (Cohen's d) of each predictor.

	GA	Frontal Total	Temporal Total	Parietal Total	Occipital Total	CC posterior	CC Total	Global score	CC length	Splenium thickness
Titmus stereo Fly	-0.448	-0.026	0.059	0.564	0.027	0.051	0.300	0.008	-0.526	-0.016
TVPS -Visual Discrimination	0	0.003	0.011	0	0	0	0.011	0	-0.534	0
TVPS -Spatial Relationships	^a 0.000	0	0	-0.002	-0.003	0	0	0	-0.390	0
TVPS -Form Constancy	-0.275	-0.005	-0.028	<i>0.116</i>	0.003	-0.038	^a 0.000	^a 0.000	-0.442	-0.062
TVPS -Visual Figure-Ground	0.002	-0.029	0.377	-0.333	-0.433	0	-0.005	0	-0.554	-0.125
Beery- Visuomotor integration	<i>-0.186</i>	<i>0.141</i>	0.202	<i>0.193</i>	0.349	<i>0.175</i>	<i>0.196</i>	0.239	-0.079	<i>-0.161</i>

^aThe average estimate is less than 0.001

Abbreviations: GA, gestational age; CC, corpus callosum; TVPS-4, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; NA, data not available since we were unable to fit an adequate model for this outcome. The estimate of each individual predictors was used as effect sizes (Cohen's d) and interpreted as tiny (< 0.10), very small (0.10-0.19) in italics, small (0.20-0.49) in bold italics, moderate (0.50-0.79) in bold, large (0.80-1.19), very large (1.20-1.99) and huge (≥ 2.00).⁴³

Figure A1. Flow chart describing the study cohort.

Abbreviations: uCP, unilateral cerebral palsy; MRI, magnetic resonance imaging; GA, gestational age; CC, corpus callosum; FrACT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; FCVIQ, Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire.

Table S1. Prevalence of children with unilateral cerebral palsy ($n=41$) with impairments on the visual assessments, brain damage on the semiquantitative scale, and corpus callosum biometry below the normative median.

Visual assessments	<i>N</i> of children (%)
FraCT	4 (8)
Titmus Stereo Fly	14 (34)
TVPS -Visual Discrimination	14 (34)
TVPS -Spatial Relationships	11 (27)
TVPS -Form Constancy	12 (29)
TVPS -Visual Figure-Ground	12 (29)
TVPS -Visual Closure	18 (44)
Beery- Visuomotor integration	24 (60)*
Brain damage	<i>N</i> of children (%)
Frontal Total	37 (90)
Temporal Total	38 (93)
Parietal Total	36 (88)
Occipital Total	36 (88)
Thalamic Total	16 (39)
Subcortical	31 (76)
CC posterior	28 (68)
CC Total	31 (76)
Global score	39 (95)
^a CC length	27 (68)*
^a Splenium thickness	30 (73)

^a Results calculated as above (0) or below (1) the normative median.³⁴

Abbreviations: *N*, Number of children with brain damage on the semi-quantitative scale or corpus callosum biometry below the median out of the total sample of 41 children with uCP; %, percentage of children out of the total sample of 41 children (* results calculated out of 40 due to NA data); FraCT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition.

Table S2. Partial Spearman Rank's correlations corrected for gestational age between the results of the visual assessments and the MRI scores on the semiquantitative scale and corpus callosum biometry in children with unilateral CP.

<i>Visual assessments</i>		Semiquantitative scale								CC biometry		
		Frontal Total	Temporal Total	Parietal Total	Occipital Total	Thalamic Total	Subcortical	CC Total	CC posterior	Global score	CC length	Splenium
<i>FraCT</i>	r_s	0.321	0.393	0.529*	0.378	0.107	0.252	0.349	0.245	0.494*	-0.463*	-0.391
	p	0.110	0.051	0.011	0.060	0.592	0.186	0.080	0.194	0.017	0.019	0.051
<i>Titmus Stereo Fly</i>	r_s	-0.459*	-0.456*	-0.417*	-0.267	-0.318	-0.260	-0.611**	-0.458*	-0.555*	0.483*	0.369
	p	0.019	0.019	0.037	0.169	0.110	0.172	0.004	0.019	0.011	0.018	0.064
<i>TVPS-4 Visual Discrimination</i>	r_s	-0.318	-0.360	-0.082	0.094	-0.077	-0.264	-0.271	-0.118	-0.280	0.538*	0.124
	p	0.110	0.068	0.658	0.621	0.677	0.169	0.165	0.570	0.149	0.011	0.558
<i>TVPS-4 -Spatial Relationships</i>	r_s	-0.300	-0.319	-0.097	-0.009	0.111	-0.100	-0.248	-0.167	-0.229	0.308	0.112
	p	0.131	0.110	0.614	0.964	0.591	0.613	0.189	0.397	0.227	0.126	0.591
<i>TVPS-4 -Form Constancy</i>	r_s	-0.367	-0.288	-0.295	-0.028	0.006	-0.162	-0.315	-0.107	-0.330	0.526*	0.428*
	p	0.064	0.138	0.135	0.893	0.972	0.412	0.112	0.592	0.102	0.011	0.031
<i>TVPS-4 -Visual Figure Ground</i>	r_s	-0.292	-0.374	-0.084	-0.013	-0.097	-0.266	-0.286	-0.190	-0.321	0.345	0.120
	p	0.135	0.061	0.657	0.957	0.614	0.169	0.141	0.324	0.110	0.091	0.569
<i>TVPS-4 -Visual Closure</i>	r_s	-0.330	-0.487*	-0.298	-0.264	0.106	-0.184	-0.223	-0.191	-0.381	0.245	0.261
	p	0.102	0.018	0.131	0.169	0.592	0.341	0.240	0.324	0.059	0.198	0.172
<i>Beery- Visuomotor integration</i>	r_s	-0.382	-0.402*	-0.253	-0.464*	-0.073	-0.295	-0.412*	-0.449*	-0.490*	0.318	0.295
	p	0.060	0.049	0.189	0.019	0.692	0.135	0.042	0.023	0.018	0.119	0.135
<i>FCVIQ</i>	r_s	0.478*	0.505*	0.371	0.201	0.142	0.261	0.411*	0.210	0.486*	-0.542*	-0.456*
	p	0.018	0.017	0.064	0.307	0.496	0.175	0.042	0.283	0.018	0.011	0.021

Cases were excluded pairwise. Significant results are shown in bold type: * $p \leq 0.05$, ** $p \leq 0.01$.

Abbreviations: r_s , Spearman correlation interpreted as no or negligible correlation (<0.30), low (0.30–0.49), moderate (0.50–0.69), high (0.70–0.89), and very high (≥ 0.90).³⁵ CC, corpus callosum; FrACT, Freiburg Visual Acuity Test; TVPS, Test of Visual Perceptual Skills, Fourth Edition; Beery, Beery-Buktenica Test of Visual-Motor Integration, Sixth Edition; FCVIQ, Flemish cerebral visual impairment questionnaire.